

Chemical Examination of the Seeds of *Abrus precatorius*, Linn. Part I.

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Abrus precatorius or Jequirity as it is known in English, Gunja in Sanskrit, Rati in Hindustani and Kunch in Bengali is a plant of the natural order *Leguminosæ*. It is grown in India and other hot countries. It is a perennial twiner with numerous stems. Seeds from 3 to 5 are contained in pods which are from $1\frac{1}{2}$ to $1\frac{3}{4}$ in. long and $\frac{1}{2}$ in. wide. The seeds are usually bright scarlet, with a black spot on the top and are highly polished. The average weight of the seed is 1.75 grains. There are three varieties of the seed *e.g.*, scarlet, white and black, but the findings of the present paper are on the scarlet one. The seeds are used in India by the goldsmiths as weight. The leaves, seeds and the roots of *Abrus precatorius* have been articles of Hindu materia medica from a very remote period. Internally, the seeds are described as poisonous and useful in affections of the nervous system, and, externally, in skin diseases, ulcers, affections of the hair, leprosy, etc., (Dymock, "Pharmacographia Indica," Vol. I. p. 430).

Warden and Waddell ("Non-bacillar nature of *Abrus* poison," Calcutta, 1884) have given the name 'abrin' to the poisonous principle of Jequirity. They showed that abrin was closely allied to 'plant albumin' but did not enter into any details as to whether it consisted of one or more proteids. Martin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1887, 52, 990) proved the presence of two proteids, a globulin and an albumose in the kernels and the toxic action of Jequirity is attributed to them. Dr. Warden ("Pharmacographia Indica," 1890, Vol. I, p. 442) claims to have succeeded in isolating an acid from the seeds, which he named as 'abric acid' and represented it by the formula $C_{21}H_{24}O_4N_3$, which is not in agreement with the "law of even number of atoms." He also obtained a small quantity of pungent volatile oil. But he gives no details as to how abric acid was isolated. Abrin (Haas and Hill, "Chemistry of Plant Products," 1928, Vol. I. p. 371) has been suspected to have the same properties as ricin which occurs in *Ricinus*.

Their toxic characters have been attributed partly to the presence of ptomaine bodies and largely to bacterial toxins, a class of substance related to albumoses.

The above represents the work that has hitherto been done on the seeds of *Abrus precatorius*. A systematic analysis of the seeds was, therefore, undertaken with a view to study the exact chemical nature of the poisonous constituents. Two definite products, one nitrogen containing and another a glucoside, *vis.*, abrine and abralin, have now been isolated. Some quantity of a non-drying yellow oil has also been obtained. The properties of these substances have been described in the experimental part.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The scarlet variety of the seed of *Abrus precatorius* was obtained from the local market. The red seed-coat was removed by coarsely crushing the seeds in a grinding machine. The outer coating constituted 80 p. c. of the entire seed. The yellow kernels were very hard.

The powdered kernel (50 g.) was freed from oil by extraction with petroleum ether in the cold and the oil-free powder on cold aqueous extraction gave a cloudy precipitate with ethyl alcohol which probably contained some enzymes. The powder on completely burning left 2.5 p. c. of a white residue (ash) which on qualitative analysis was found to contain iron, aluminium, calcium, silicon, magnesium, sulphate and phosphate.

For complete analysis 1.5 kg. of the crushed kernels were exhaustively extracted in a round bottomed extraction flask with 5 litres petroleum ether (b. p. 35-60°) till a portion of the extract did not give any oily residue on evaporation of the solvent. From the petroleum ether extract 85 g. of a yellowish brown, pungent, non-drying oil was obtained. The oil-free powder was successively extracted with rectified spirit. The first few extracts were yellow in colour and after that colourless extracts were obtained which deposited white needles in small quantities on evaporation of the solvent. The substance seemed to be very little soluble in alcohol and, therefore, the extraction was done about 20 times in order to recover the crystalline product completely from the powder. The powder became almost colourless after the extractions. The total alcoholic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure when a brown syrup having white crystalline suspension was obtained. The liquid, which had a

disagreeable smell, was allowed to stand for about a week when the quantity of the crystalline product increased and settled at the bottom. It was filtered and washed with water. The dried crude product, which weighed 13 g. turned brown at 210° and completely melted at 247°. This substance was moderately soluble in hot water from which snow-white needles were obtained melting at 295° and having a molecular formula $C_{12}H_{14}O_2N_2$. It has been named as 'abrine' by the present authors. Warden (*loc. cit.*) must have got this substance in an impure form which gave him a wrong analytical data and made him to suspect the compound to be acidic in nature.

Abrine is insoluble in all organic solvents excepting alcohol in which it is slightly soluble. Neutral ferric chloride, lead acetate or subacetate, silver nitrate and calcium chloride have no effect on the substance. Phosphomolybdic acid produces a white precipitate which soon changes to yellowish green and finally to grey colour. Eardman's and Fröhde's reagents give yellow coloration with abrine. Gold chloride solution produces a yellowish turbidity which darkens and in about 1 minute becomes violet, which, however, throws down a blue-black precipitate on addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid. Platinic chloride solution seems to have no effect on the substance in the cold, but on heating and allowing it to cool a brown gelatinous precipitate settles at the bottom. Abrine is non-responsive to the rest of the alkaloidal reagents. It dissolves readily in hydrochloric acid and on complete evaporation of the solvent long silky needles of the hydrochloride of abrine are obtained which quickly dissolve in water. The hydrochloride gives all the reactions of the free base as described above, excepting with gold and platinic chloride solutions. The hydrochloride, however, gives a white precipitate with phosphotungstic acid which turns brown in about 5 minutes. From the above reactions it can be said that abrine, is semi-alkaloidal in character. It is tasteless when pure and therefore may be classed in the group of non-bitter alkaloids.

The thick mother liquor after the separation of abrine was diluted with water and on addition of lead acetate solution a thick yellow flocculent precipitate of strong disagreeable odour, was obtained. The precipitate was washed free from lead and decomposed with sulphuretted hydrogen. The yellow filtrate on complete evaporation of water gave a brown sticky mass from which no chemically pure substance could be isolated. The product contained considerable amount of reducing sugars.

The filtrate of the above lead salt gave a bright yellow bulky precipitate with lead subacetate solution. The purified lead salt was decomposed with sulphuretted hydrogen in alcoholic suspension. The yellow filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure and on complete evaporation of the solvent a yellow deposit was obtained. It was non-crystalline in character and melted at 105° after remaining over calcium chloride in a vacuum desiccator for 2 days. This substance which has a molecular formula $C_{13}H_{14}O_7$, has been named as 'abralin' by the present authors. Abralin does not reduce Fehling's solution and Tollen's reagent, but both are readily reduced if the compound is previously hydrolysed by warming with concentrated hydrochloric acid. It does not produce any coloration or precipitate with the usual alkaloid reagents. Abralin has an astringent and mild bitter taste and produces a dark coloration with neutral ferric chloride solution, which turns red on dilution. The physiological examinations of abrine and abralin are in progress.

The oil on purification with Fuller's earth and animal charcoal became lighter in colour. It did not contain nitrogen and sulphur and was tasteless. The oil was optically active and gave a *dextro* rotation of $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +0.39$. This small rotation must be due to the presence of sterols in the oil. The oil burnt with an absolutely non-luminous flame and gave the following constants.

Mixture	0.78 p. c.
Specific gravity at 25°	0.9139
Refractive index at 25°	1.4662
Acid value	2.44
Saponification value	191.7
Hebner value	88.06
Acetyl value	nil
Iodine value	95.1
Unsaponifiable matter	1.68

Abrine.—Abrine dissolves in concentrated nitric acid with orange red colour which becomes yellow on dilution. In strong sulphuric acid it dissolves with yellow colour. When very slowly crystallised from water about 1 cm. long star shaped needles are obtained. [Found: C, 65.78; H, 6.46; N, 13.15; M. W. (cryoscopic in phenol),

221. $C_{12}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires, C, 66.08; H, 6.42; N, 12.84 per cent. M.W., 218).

Abralin.—In concentrated nitric acid abralin dissolves with red colour, which becomes orange yellow on dilution. In strong sulphuric acid it dissolves with a yellow colour which slowly darkens and finally becomes deep red. On dilution the colour is discharged and a yellow flocculent precipitate separates, which is the aglucone of the glucoside. Abralin was optically active, having a *laevo* rotation of $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -27.37$ in aqueous solution. [Found: C, 54.98; H, 5.29; M. W. (cryoscopic in phenol), 286, (lead salt), 281. $C_{13}H_{14}O_7$ requires, C, 55.32; H, 4.96 per cent. M.W., 282).

Further work on the constitutions of abrine and abralin is in progress.

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